

Introductory questions

- Present us and the NGEA project.
 - The project agreement handles confidentiality. Interview data will only be available to the researchers performing the study. All data will be anonymized prior to publication. Your company will review the article prior to publication.
 - May we record?
 - What is your current role?
 - Time in current role?
 - Previous experience?
 - Education background?
 - Which organization/department are you part of?
 - Describe the work within your area of responsibility. From a recipient/user/customer perspective, what is delivered?
1. If the goal is to be faster in development, what does that mean for your department?
 - (a) What obstacles do you see for getting there? Can you give examples?
 - (b) How autonomously can you/your organization/group work today?

Organization

2. We see that there are many dependencies between units, departments, lines, and projects at [Company]. Is your development speed affected by (internal) dependencies, and if so how?
 - (a) How often do you, for solutions where you are responsible, need to anchor these with other organizations/departments? Can you give examples?
 - (b) How does your current role setup affect speed? Can you give examples?
 - (c) Are there any unnecessary dependencies towards other departments/groups?
 - i. What would you like to do to decrease these dependencies?
 - ii. What obstacles do you see? Can you give examples?
3. Is your development speed affected by external dependencies, and if so how?
 - (a) What advantages and disadvantages do you see of internal and external software development, respectively? What do you have today?

- (b) What would you like the division/allocation between them to be?
- (c) How do you see yourselves getting there?

Processes and artifacts/deliverables

- 4. How is your development speed affected by how requirements work is done today?
 - (a) What would be the optimal way of working at your department?
 - (b) What obstacles do you see for achieving that? Can you give examples?
 - (c) Are there any obstacles among the processes?
 - (d) Do you in some case need to go outside or past the processes? (What is your current way of working?)
- 5. Are the deliverables you have (documents, requirements, technical things etc.) shaped in such a way that you can be fast? Can you give examples?
 - (a) How long time does it take before you receive feedback (on deliverables)?
 - (b) Do you produce deliverables you think are unnecessary? Can you give examples?
 - (c) Does your department have any need for *Continuous Integration*?
 - i. What would you like to do to be able to integrate more often?
 - ii. What obstacles do you see for getting there?
- 6. Are there any other aspects preventing you from working fast and independently?
 - (a) (If no answer) procurements, projects vs. products, ISO26262 etc?

Misc

- 7. (In an ideal world) how could lead times be shortened?
 - (a) Solution horizon one year.
 - (b) Solution horizon five years.
- 8. Who else should we talk to?
- 9. Is there anything you would like to add?

Thank you!